

A STUDY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING WITH REFERENCE TO NAMAKKAL DISTRICT

Dr. N. Senthilkumar* & KL. Chandramohan**

* Research Supervisor in Commerce, Kandaswami Kandar's College, P. Velur, Namakkal, Tamilnadu

** Research Scholar in Commerce, Kandaswami Kandar's College, P. Velur, Namakkal, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Dr. N. Senthilkumar & KL. Chandramohan, "A Study on Customer Satisfaction towards Online Shopping with Reference to Namakkal District", International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 348-351, 2018.

Copy Right: © IJCRME, 2018 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

Online shopping is most trendy phenomenon in the present world. The study aims to identify the customers satisfaction towards online shopping in Namakkal district. The study was based on questionnaire with a sample of 100 respondents. The findings of the study are analyzed using simple percentage analysis, chi-square test and friedman ranking test. Findings reveal that age, gender and educational qualification have significant association with customers level of satisfaction towards online shopping. The study also concludes that 24 hours service was the first satisfaction factor of the customers towards online shopping.

Key Words: Online, Trend, Shopping, Customers, Satisfaction, Purchasing, Market & etc.,

Introduction:

Online shopping is most trendy phenomenon in the present world. It is more convenient to sit at one place and shop the product of our choice without moving from place to place. Apart from gender, all ages visit the online shopping websites regularly and buy the necessities of life. Online shopping is the process of researching and purchasing products or services through the Internet. The earliest online stores went into business in 1992 and online shopping take a significant segment of the retail market during the first decade of the twenty-first century.

Online shopping usage has grown rapidly over the past years and it has become common means for delivering and trading information, services and goods and it is growing tremendously in the current business scenario it is imperative to study how consumers' make purchase decisions on the Internet.

Factors That Affecting Customers Buying Behaviors:

- ✓ Personal characteristics of a person is an important factor affecting the purchase decision process. Personal factors include age, gender, occupation, income status, education, life style.
- ✓ Psychological characteristics of a person make customers to ask themselves, should they look a better price or should they shop online more often and perception is one of the important factors that examine the security of the web site or the quality of the product.
- ✓ Social characteristics of a person influence the online consumers have virtual communities, consisting of discussion groups on a web site and family is one of this reference groups.
- ✓ Cultural characteristics of a person of the consumers set values and beliefs in the early ages therefore person's wants and needs are driven by this base feature.

Need of the Study:

- ✓ To know the present scenario of the online shopping in Namakkal District.
- ✓ To find out the people's satisfaction towards online shopping products.

Review of Literature:

Dr. Mübin Kiyici (2012) revealed students' online shopping behavior and online shopping activities. The study shows that male student's teachers are more familiar and have more positive attitude than female student teacher. The study also founded that teacher and students who have more monthly income and have more internet self efficacy have positive attitude and intension to shop online. The study also concludes that participants, who have credit card, have more familiarity and less anxiety concerning internet shopping.

Dr. Gagandeep Nagra, Dr. R Gopal (2013) observed that the potential growth of online shopping has triggered the idea of conducting a study on online shopping in India. The study has used Qualitative and Quantitative research methods to study the impact of demographic variables of consumers on on-line shopping parameters like satisfaction with on-line shopping, future purchase intention, frequency of on-line shopping, numbers of items purchased, and overall spend on on-line shopping. The data needed for the study was collected through well structured Questionnaires. The findings reveal that on-line shopping in India is significantly affected by various demographic variables like age, gender, marital status, family size and income. The findings of the study could be further used by the researchers and practitioners for conducting future studies in the similar area.

Lakshmi. S (2016) revealed that there are millions of people online any time and they all are a potential consumer in the online market. According to this study the most important thing for organizations is to understand what are consumer wants and needs in this competitive business environment. The study also reveals that customer buying behaviors are influenced by different factors such as culture, social class, references group relation, family, salary level and salary independency, age, gender etc. and so they show different customer behaviors.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To find the factors that determines the customer’s level of satisfaction of towards online shopping in Namakkal District

Hypothesis:

- ✓ There is no significant association between gender and satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant association between age and satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant association between educational qualification and satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant association between monthly income and satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant association between type of family and satisfaction.

Limitations:

- ✓ The result of the study is based upon the views expressed by the respondents of Namakkal District.
- ✓ The statistical tools used to analyse the data have their own limitations.
- ✓ All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.

Research Methodology:

Area of the Study: The research study was done in Namakkal District.

Nature and Source of Data: The study is based on questionnaire method; Both Primary data and secondary data have been used for this study.

- ✓ Primary data has been collected from various customers in Namakkal District.
- ✓ Secondary data have been collected from related journals, Magazines and textbooks.

Statistical Tools Used for the Study:

- ✓ Simple percentage analysis
- ✓ ANOVA
- ✓ Friedman’s Ranking Test

Sampling Used: 100 respondents were selected by convenient sampling method.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Demographic profile of the Respondents

Factors	No of Respondents n=100	Percentage
Gender		
Male	60	60
Female	40	40
Age(years)		
Up to 30	50	50
30 to 50	34	34
Above 50	16	16
Educational qualification		
Up to School Level	20	20
UG	46	46
PG	34	34
Monthly Income		
Up to Rs. 15,000	46	46
Above Rs.15,000	54	54
Type of Family		
Joint Family	34	34
Nuclear family	66	66

Inference: Table No.1 describes the demographic profile of the respondents towards Online shopping. Out of 100 customers who were taken for the study: it has been identified that most (60%) of the customers are male, (50%) whose age group is below 30 years, most (46%) of the customers are under graduate, the monthly income of (54%) customers is above Rs.15, 000 and (66%) customers belong to nuclear family.

Table 2: Source of knowledge about online shopping

Source	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Own	12	12
Friends & Relatives	54	54
Media	34	34

Total	100	100
-------	-----	-----

Inference: The above table shows that, out of 100 numbers of respondents 12% of the customers came to know about this online shopping through their own knowledge, 54% of the customers through friends & relatives and remaining 34% of the customers through Media.

Table 3: Level of Satisfaction towards Online shopping

Source	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Low	32	32
Medium	48	48
High	30	30
Total	100	100

Inference: The above table shows that, out of 100 respondents, level of satisfaction is found to be low with regard to 32% of the customers, in case of 48% customers level of satisfaction is medium and 30% customers are highly satisfied towards Online shopping.

Table 4: Relationship between Demographic Profile and Level of Satisfaction

	χ^2 Value	Table Value	Remarks
Gender	7.89	5.991	S
Age	12.56	9.488	S
Educational Qualification	14.89	9.488	S
Monthly Income	4.425	5.991	NS
Type of family	3.445	5.991	NS

Table 4 depicts the relationship between selected demographic variables. It is clear that, the calculated Chi-square value is greater than table value at five percent level there does exist any significant association between gender, age, educational qualification level of satisfaction towards online shopping. Thus the null hypothesis is rejected. The calculated Chi-square value is less than the table value at five percent level, there exists no significant association between monthly income, type of family and level of satisfaction towards online shopping. Thus the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 5: Customers Satisfaction – Friedman Rank Test

Factors	Average Rank	Rank
Low Price	3.7	4
Easy Availability	2.8	5
24 hours	6.8	1
Convenient	5.2	3
Variety of Choice	4.6	2
Quality	1.2	6

The above table shows about the Friedman Rank Test for policyholder’s satisfaction were the level of significance is at 0.000 which shows that there is a relationship between the ranks given. The satisfaction factor of the customers towards the online shopping through Friedman rank test, it is found that majority of the customers are satisfied 24 hours service, variety of choice, convenient, low price, easy availability and quality. Thus, it found from the above table that most of the customers are satisfied on 24 hours service towards online shopping.

Conclusion:

Online shopping is one of the most interesting, widely accepted, highly appreciated shopping. It is an important facilitator for human and human use this medium for every need of his life. Online shopping has made consumers more effective and efficient in their shopping behaviour and also there is a need for educating the consumers and awareness about online shopping. The research concludes that customer satisfaction plays a vital role in determining the usage of online shopping. The overall results prove that the respondents are given a positive step towards online shopping.

References:

1. Dr. Mübin Kiyici, Internet Shopping Behavior of College of Education Students, The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology – July 2012, Volume 11 Issue 3
2. Dr. Gagandeep Nagra , Dr. R. Gopal, An Study of Factors Affecting On Online Shopping Behavior of Consumers , International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Volume 3, Issue 6, June 2013 1 ISSN 2250-3153 www.ijsrp.org
3. Lakshmi.S, Consumer Buying Behavior towards Online Shopping Lakshmi. S International Journal Of Research - Granthaalayah [60-65] Management, Vol.4 (Iss.8: Se): August, 2016] ISSN- 2350-0530(O) Issn- 2394-3629 (P)
4. Ali, Pervaiz; Sankaran, Sudha, “Online Shopping Consumer Satisfaction and Loyalty in Norway”, Published by Lap Lambert Academic Publishing (2011)

5. Upasan Kanchan (2015), A Study Of Online Purchase Behavior of Consumers in India, ICTACT Journal of Management Studies, ISSN 2395, Vol-01, Issue-03
6. Ashok Kumar Chandra, Devendra Kumar Sinha (2013), "Factors Affecting the Online Shopping Behaviour: A Study with Reference to Bhilai Durg", International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences ISSN: 2278-6236 Vol. 2, No. 5, May 2013, P.No: 160.
7. Prashant Singh (2014), "Consumer's Buying Behaviour Towards Online Shopping a Case Study of Flipkart.Com User's in Lucknow City", National Monthly Refereed Journal of Research in Commerce and Management , Volume III, February'14 ISSN – 2277-1166 .
8. Gupta, A., Bansal, R., & Bansal, A. (2013). Online Shopping: A Shining Future. International Journal of Techno-Management Research, 1 (1), 1-10.
9. Prof. Ashih Bhatt (2014), Consumers Attitude Towards Online Shopping in Selected Region of Gujarat, Journal of Marketing Management, ISSN-2333-6080, Vol.-02, No.-02
10. Ravjot Kaur, Gurmeet Kaur, Aman Kumar, Gaurav Kumar (2015), Consumers Attitude Towards Online Shopping in Chandigarh, International Journal of Management and Social Sciences, Research, ISSN 2319-4421, Vol-4, No.-3
11. K. Veerakumar (2016) article titled "A Research on Quality Factors Influencing Online Shopping" International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education, Vol-I, Issue-II, July – 2016. P.No.1-5.